

THE GROWTH OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN TAMIL NADU

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Abstract:

This paper focuses on the growth of educational system and the patterns of higher education in Tamil Nadu. Also it traces the various system, educational practices as well as institutional data that indicate the existence of Tamil Nadu. Education is playing pivotal task on reducing poverty and socio-economic unfairness in rural and urban areas of India. It removes the economic disparities and societal upheavals in the country. The education has been responsible for the human empowerment as well. The importance of educational service is forever growing in India. The public and private sectors contribute to delivering education from primary education to higher education. Education is the basic right of every citizen in India. Mainly, education forms the significance of inclusive growth of the country. This study explores the public and private higher educational institutions and literacy level of Tamil Nadu.

Key Words: Education, Growth, System & Educational Institutions

Introduction:

Education is a basic human right and is necessary for enjoying many other rights. It is transformative and empowering and a means for accessing broad economic, social, political and cultural benefits. Education contributes to building more just societies through reducing poverty and inequalities. No country has ever climbed the human development ladder without steady investment in educational system. Education in every sense is one of the fundamental factors of development. It provides one with the best opportunities of becoming successful in the modern society. In terms of knowledge, qualities, skills, attitudes, and capacities, education enables individuals to become conscious subjects of their growth and active responsible participants in a systematic process of building a new world order. Education enriches people's understanding of themselves and of the world. It improves the quality of their lives and leads to broad social benefits to individuals and society. Education raises people's productivity and creativity and promotes entrepreneurship and technological advances. The study attempted to explore the systems in the higher educational institutions in Tamil Nadu state. Higher education plays essential development of country and it will accelerate economic growth of our nation and improvement and development in all the fields. India believed in education as an agency for changing economic and social lives of the people. The destiny of India is now being shaped in her class rooms. It is education that determines the level of prosperity, welfare and security of the people. This belief in an almost automatic relationship between education and development resulted in large sums being allocated both in budgets and in investment programmes. Specifically the aim is split into operational objectives of studying the historical growth of education in Tamilnadu.

Objectives:

An attempt is made to design the dimension of education in the progressive Tamil Nadu with the following objectives to understand the literacy rates in India and Tamil Nadu, and to analyze the distribution of higher educational institutions in India and Tamil Nadu.

- ✓ To understand the concepts of growth and educational system
- ✓ To know the principles of education
- ✓ To differentiate the growth of education between public and private sectors
- ✓ To identify the factors influence the systems
- ✓ To analyze the impact of literacy rate

Meaning and Definition of Growth:

The Encyclopedia of Britannica defines 'growth' as an increase in the size or the amount of an entity. The word growth is used for all those structural and physiological changes that takes place within individual during the process of maturation. Growth is change in size, in proportion, disappearance of old features and acquisition of new ones (Hurlock, 1959) Growth refers to structural and physiological changes. (Crow & Crow 1962). The term 'growth' refers to the change in the physical or physiological structure. This shows that 'growth' is physiological change.

Methodology:

This study focuses on educational institutions and its system in Tamil Nadu have been outlined an account of higher education institutions which deliver general and educational system is explored. Here simple growth rate and percentage for analyzing the higher educational situation at inclusive level have been employed.

Definition of the Education:

The term 'Education' is defined in many ways. To the Biologists, education is largely adaptation; to the Psychologists it is synonymous with learning; to the Philosopher and especially to the educator it reflects the school of thought to which he belongs. An extreme conservative views education as a protective process of the state to preserve the status quo, whereas a progressive regards education as self expression to assist the individual to do better, things he would do any way.

History of Education in India:

A monastic order of education under the supervision of a guru was a favored form of education for the nobility in ancient India. The knowledge in these orders was often related to the tasks a section of the society had to perform. The priest class, the Brahmins, was imparted knowledge of religion, philosophy, and other ancillary branches while the warrior classes, the Kshatriya, were trained in the various aspects of warfare. The business classes, the Vaishya, were taught their trade and the lowered class of the Shudras was generally deprived of educational advantages. The book of laws, the Manusmriti, and the treatise on statecraft the Arthashastra were among the influential works of this era which reflect the outlook and understanding of the world at the time.

Apart from the monastic orders, institutions of higher learning and universities flourished in India well before the Common Era, and continued to deliver education into the Common Era. Secular Buddhist institutions cropped up along with monasteries. These institutions imparted practical education, e.g. medicine. A number of urban learning centres became increasingly visible from the period between 200 BCE to 400 CE. The important urban centres of learning were Taxila and Nalanda, among others. These institutions systematically imparted knowledge and attracted a number of foreign students to study topics such as logic, grammar, medicine, metaphysics, arts and crafts. By the time of the visit of the Islamic scholar Alberuni (973-1048 CE), India already had a sophisticated system of mathematics and science in place, and had made a number of inventions and discoveries.

With the arrival of the British Raj in India a class of Westernized elite was versed in the Western system of education which the British had introduced. This system soon became solidified in India as a number of primary, secondary, and tertiary centres for education cropped up during the colonial era. Between 1867 and 1941 the British increased the percentage of the population in Primary and Secondary Education from around 0.6% of the population in 1867 to over 3.5% of the population in 1941. However this was much lower than the equivalent figures for Europe where in 1911 between 8 and 18% of the population were in Primary and Secondary education. Additionally literacy was also improved. In 1901 the literacy rate in India was only about 5% though by Independence it was nearly 20%.

The Growth of the Educational System:

Following independence in 1947, Maulana Azad, India's first education minister envisaged strong central government control over education throughout the country, with a uniform educational system. However, given the cultural and linguistic diversity of India, it was only the higher education dealing with science and technology that came under the jurisdiction of the central government. The government also held powers to make national policies for educational development and could regulate selected aspects of education throughout India. The central government of India formulated the National Policy on Education (NPE) in 1986 and also reinforced the Programme of Action (POA) in 1986. The government initiated several measures the launching of DPEP (District Primary Education Programme) and SSA (Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, India's initiative for Education for All) and setting up of Navodaya Vidyalaya and other selective schools in every district, advances in female education, inter-disciplinary research and establishment of open universities.

India's NPE also contains the National System of Education, which ensures some uniformity while taking into account regional education needs. The NPE also stresses on higher spending on education, envisaging a budget of more than 6% of the Gross Domestic Product. While the need for wider reform in the primary and secondary sectors is recognized as an issue, the emphasis is also on the development of science and technology education infrastructure.

The Growth of Higher Education:

Higher education is a powerful sector of the growth, enhance productivity, contribute to personal and social development, and reduce social inequality. The higher education institutions need to produce research with international institutions. While India has large youth population and very less number of higher education institutions function in India.

The system of higher education in India is one of the largest in the world. The system of education in India inherited a poor educational infrastructure from the colonial masters. The colonial policy focused neither on mass education nor on higher education. As a consequence, the country had to begin from scratch soon after its Independence. In order to meet the requirements of professional and technical manpower in a developing economy, the government set up the Indian Institutes of Technology, regional engineering colleges, medical colleges, arts and science colleges and universities. However, to begin with, there were only 20 universities and 500 colleges at the time of Independence. In 1990-91, there were only 179 university level and research

institutions which grew to 511 in 2006-07. During the same period, the colleges grew from 4,152 to 19,812 in the country.

The growth of the colleges during this period was high at 7.16 percent per annum compared to 4.58 percent at the university level. Tamil Nadu, the second industrialized state after Maharashtra, has registered a higher growth rate both at university level and also at college level than at the national level.

Structure of Higher Education in India:

Central Government is responsible for major policy relating to higher education in the country. It provides grants to UGC and establishes central universities in the country. The Central Government is also responsible for declaration of Education Institutions as 'Deemed to be University' on the recommendation of the UGC. The higher education in India is divided into:

- ✓ University Grants Commission (UGC).
- ✓ Association of Indian Universities (AIU).
- ✓ Councils
- ✓ Other institutes of Higher Learning.
- ✓ Bilateral Bodies.

India had a glorious educational heritage. On account of the changing political, social and economic conditions, educational pattern in the country has undergone considerable changes. Education was the handmaid of religion both during the Hindu and the Muslim periods and religious organisations spared no pains to percolate the light of learning. The situation, however, changed with the advent of the British rule.

After assuming power in Bengal in 1765, the British had refused to take the responsibility for the education of the people of India and had left the task to private efforts³. However, a departure was made in 1813, as the charter-Act-of 1813 had provided means for oriental learning among the Indians⁴. Under the Act, a committee of Public Instruction was appointed to suggest measures for the better education of the peoples of India. Subsequently, instruction in oriental learning was regarded as frivolous and the Government was requested to impart useful learning to the people. Progressive leaders like Raja Ram Mohan Roy favoured the spread of English education and western learning. The Committee of Public Instruction was divided, equally as Anglicist and Orientalist, which had led to indecisiveness of the committee. Lord Macaulay, the President of the Committee of Public Instruction cast his vote with the Anglicist philosophy and in his famous minute of 2nd February, 1835^m denounced the continued promotion of orientalism and emphasised the value of English education, which had tilted the balance in the letter's favour.

Then a scheme of education was prepared by the Despatch of Charleswood in 1854. It made the English language as the medium of instruction in higher education. To help the private initiative in the field of education, a grant-in-aid code was introduced. A Department of Public Instruction was created under the charge of a Director in the five provinces of Company's territories and they were asked to submit annual reports to the government. Universities were established in Bombay, Calcutta and Madras in 1857¹⁰. Hunter Commission was appointed in 1882 to review the progress of education and to enquire the manner in which effect has been given to the principles of the Despatch of 1854, Higher education had witnessed an unprecedented growth in the two decades after the Hunter's Commission report and philanthropists came forward to establish several institutions of higher learning. The Act of 1904 had widened the scope and functions of the Universities by adding teaching and research in a addition to examining the students and awarding diplomas. Inspection of affiliated colleges was provided for now the government was armed with more powers over university affairs.

The Sadler University Commission suggested the establishment of Unitary Residential Universities. The Government of India Act of 1919 transferred the education department to the provinces and placed it under the control of popularly elected ministers. The Hartog Committee of 1929 felt that the deterioration of quality was due to indiscriminate admission in educational institutions and suggested recommendations to remove the same. After Independence, Radhakrishnan Commission on University education recommended twelve years of Pre-University education, enhancement of scales of pay of University teachers and the establishment of the University Grants Commission. The UGC came into existence in 1956 and it now supervises university education and disburses grants to various universities¹⁸. The Kothari National Education Commission of 1964-65 recommended the abolition of Pre-University Course and adoption of 10+2+3 pattern of education.

Education Development in Tamil Nadu upto 1947. In the early years of the British rule, education was not the concern of the East India Company, It being a commercial organization. The Christian missionaries, who came here with the purpose of propagating their religion, had established several educational institutions in course of time. They had not only rendered valuable service to the cause of education of the Madras Presidency, but their contribution to the educational development of the people has been nowhere, so great in India as in the South. Soon, the British began to evince interest in the education of the natives to serve their religious and ecclesiastical purposes.

The allotment of a sum of one lakh of rupees for the revival and improvement of indigenous literature and encouragement of learned natives by the charter Act 21 of 1813 was not spent for 10 years. A Committee of Public Instruction was appointed by the Governor Munro in 1823 to distribute it among cultural projects and

to take measures to improve education and to direct and superintend public education. He pointed out that the expenses incurred by the government on education would be amply repaid by the improvement of the country, for the general diffusion of knowledge is inseparably followed by more orderly habits, by increasing industry, by a taste, for the comforts of life, by exertion to acquire them and by the growing prosperity of the people. The Court of Directors too, took a similar stand and emphasised that by affording facilities for higher education of the richer and more leisured sections of society, there would ultimately occur a real improvement in the outlook of the entire community. They sent a directive to *the Madras Government in the Despatch of 1830* to promote higher education but they were convinced that education among the masses could be diffused only through vernacular languages. Subsequently, a momentous decision was taken by the government in respect of the type of education and the medium of instruction imparted to Indians in accordance with *the recommendations of Lord Macaulay*.

The Government of India insisted the Madras Government to spend funds on higher education and the latter had appointed a Committee on Native Education and entrusted the task of establishing a college in the Presidency²⁷. But the Committee had felt that it was premature to open such an institution. Meanwhile the Public of Madras presented a petition signed by 70,000 people to the Governor Elphinstone on November 11, 1839 insisting on the opening of an English college in the City. They were prepared to bear the cost of expenditure of the institution by means of a levy on fees on the scholars²⁸. Lord Elphinstone set aside the recommendations of the Committee of Native Education and proposed the establishment of a central collegiate institution or a University. It was to function under the supervision of a University Board consisting of a President and 14 Governors of whom 7 were to be natives of the Province²⁹. The designation 'university' applied to this organization was not quite appropriate, for it was just an institution providing higher education. Based on the Scott University model, the university comprised of a college and a high school and the former would impart higher branches of literature, philosophy and science for the scholar³⁰. The Board chose Eyre Burton Powell as the Headmaster of the high school which was opened on 14th April 1841, which later on came to be known as the Presidency College³¹. But the response was poor not only in the attendance of students, but the authorities experienced several hardships in persuading students to join higher classes³².

Marquess of Tweeddale, the successor of Lord Elphinstone, thought it premature to open college classes in special branches like medicine, engineering and in the general arts course.³³ Sir Henry Pottinger, the next Governor of Madras reorganized the University Board with the aim of establishing and collegiate department in the Madras University in addition to the high school. The collegiate department thus established had four Professors for Mathematics and Physical Sciences, History, Economics and Philosophy, English Literature and Law. Thus after long vacillation, the college classes were opened in 1853.³⁴

However, the educational activities of the Madras Government between 1839 and 1854 were limited to a great extent. There was absence of coordination in the educational hierarchy. The efforts of the Madras Government in the initial stages pertaining to higher education did not bear fruit, and not even a single institution in the Presidency was found under the immediate control of the government³⁵. The year 1854 forms a landmark in the history of Indian education for it witnessed the appearance of an epoch-making 'Despatch', which outlined a systematic educational policy for India.³⁶ It recommended the establishment of a Department of Directorate of Public Instruction for the administration and superintendence of education in the Madras Presidency and a University in each of the Presidential Towns.

Consequently, the Directorate of Public Instruction in Madras came into being.³⁷ However, financial constraints on the part of the government provided encouragement to private individuals to establish and manage educational institutions through a system of Grant-in-Aid.³⁸ In August 1855, the first grant-in-aid rules for Madras Presidency was published. The purpose of making grants was to impart secular education to the people without bias³⁹.

The technical and professional aspects of education had received due respects from the authorities. The Medical School attained the status of a college in 1851 and designated as Madras Medical College. The Board of Revenue had set up a Revenue Board survey school to train surveyors which ultimately became the College of Engineering. The Madras School of Arts was established in 1850, and tended to create a taste for humanizing culture of fine arts among the native population⁴⁰.

Analysis and Discussion:

Literacy is conventionally understood as the skill and knowledge to read and write. Literacy has an important role of socio and economic development at urban and rural levels in India. The Registrar General and Census Commissioner of India, defined literacy is "[the ability of] a person aged 7 years and above [to] both write and read with understanding in any language". The table 1 indicates literacy rate in India and Tamil Nadu from 1961 to 2011. According to census reports for various years, the literacy rate during 1961 was 36.39 percent and at grew to 80.33 percent in 2011. As per the census 2011, 84.1 percent and 67.8 percent of people had ability on read and write skill respectively urban and rural areas.

Literacy Rate 1961-2011			
Year	Persons	Males	Females
1	2	3	4
1961	36.39	51.59	21.06
1971	45.40	59.54	30.92
1981	54.39	68.05	40.43
1991	62.66	73.75	51.33
2001	73.47	82.33	64.55
2011	80.33	86.81	73.86

Note: Literacy rates for 1961 and 1971 related to population aged five years and above.

The rates for the years 1981 to 2011 related to the population aged seven years and above. Establishment of Madras University The University of Madras was incorporated by an Act of the Legislative Council of India on 5th September, 1857.⁴¹ London University of the day served as a model for the creation of the Madras University which functioned as examining and affiliating body in initial days⁴². The University at first was housed in the Presidency College, and then moved to the Senate House in 1873. The first B.A. Degree examination of the University was held in February 1858. The Despatch of 1854 had also suggested the establishment of Professorships in the Universities for the purpose of delivering lectures in various branches of learning. But Marquess of Dalhousie, Governor-General of India, declared that there is no need for the duplication of lecturing work done by the colleges and the Acts of incorporation which established the Universities omitted all references to the creation of Professorships in the Universities⁴³. The work of the university naturally increased with the growth of new colleges. A. J. Arbuthnot, the Director of Public Instruction wrote to the government in 1860 in which he had stated that the standard for the uncovenanted civil service examination was much lower than that of the university, which had discouraged many candidates from resorting to the university examinations and to the courses of study leading upto them.⁴⁶ But this feature was soon rectified, and the university examinations were co-ordinate with those held for the recruitment of personnel for the public services, and this gave the university education a material value in popular estimation.

In 1882, the government of India appointed an Education Commission with a view to enquire the manner in which effect has been given to the principles of the Despatch of 1854 end to suggest such measures as it may think desirable in order to the further carrying out of the policy therein laid down. W.W. Hunter was appointed as the President of the Commission and Rev. William Miller, and P. Ranganatha Mudaliar, Professor of Mathematics, Presidency College, Madras, had the honour of serving as members of the commission from the Madras Presidency ⁴⁷.

The Commission had not only commended the good work done by the colleges under the jurisdiction of the Madras University, but had taken the stand of transferring some of the government colleges to the management of local bodies in order to encourage popular interest in higher education.

Boards of Studies In 1884, Boards of Studies were created in the place of expert committees constituted annually. It comprised of Fellows of University possessing special qualifications in the respective branches of knowledge. They have to choose text-books for various examinations and to determine the syllabi⁴⁸. A degree in teaching was instituted for the first time in 1885. For quite a long time, after the establishment of the Madras University, the women of the Presidency did not avail the opportunity of collegiate education. Though in the past, women were provided, with education, social conditions of the medieval and later times not only secluded women, but made the society to neglect their education. It was increasingly realized that a society composed of educated men and uneducated women can never be a progressive society. Thus by 1904, the Madras Presidency had 3 colleges for women (second grade) ⁴⁹.

The Act of 1904, widened the scope and functions of the Universities by including teaching and research in addition to the original responsibilities of affiliating educational institutions and conducting examinations. The Act had increased the control of the government over the Universities. The University Act of 1923 made the Vice-Chancellor a full-time executive. Till then, the Vice-Chancellorship was regarded as honorary post to be filled by a prominent man who would attend to the affairs of the University in his leisure time. The framers of the Act had encouraged the establishment of unitary and residential university and thus Annamalai University came into existence in 1928-29. The council of affiliated colleges was created within the framework of the university bodies to safeguard the interests of the affiliated colleges. However, it was abolished in 1929 and as compensation; the strength of the academic council was increased. There were 41 Arts and Sciences colleges in 1932-33 of which 36 were for men and 5 for women.⁵⁰ There were 43 Arts colleges in 1937-38 and 42 in 1939-40.⁵¹

The Educational Development in Tamil Nadu from 1947 to Present:

With regard to Tamil Nadu the growth in higher educational service is phenomenal. This state has witnessed a remarkable progress not only in traditional streams like general education and professional education but many colleges have been upgraded as autonomous colleges and even the government colleges obtained autonomous status. Basing on the reports of Radhakrishnan Commission on university education, and

the Secondary Education Commission, Pre-University Course was started in all the colleges replacing the Intermediate course from the academic year 1956-57. In the next year, the three year degree course was introduced. The dissatisfaction over the Intermediate course which was neither a collegiate course nor a High School course led to this change. In 1945, the Syndicate of the Madras University at the request of the Academic Council decided to make provision in the university laws permitting to offer instruction and to examine candidates through the media of their mother tongue. As a result the Arts Colleges at Salem and Coimbatore offered instruction through Tamil in the Intermediate course in History and Logic and National College, Trichy started Tamil medium in 1947- 48.

In fulfilling the stipulation that the University should send Commissions to inspect the affiliated colleges, such inspections had taken place in 1928, 1934, 1946 and 1955 besides the routine annual inspections. These Commissions brought to the notice of the University authorities several drawbacks in the aided institutions. As the managements and Trust Boards meddled with the internal administration of the colleges, the University was forced to bring pressure to restrain them from doing so. As a result the Principal of the institution was not only included in the Governing body but the internal administration was to be handled by the Principal with the help of a council.

The Kothari Education Commission

The Kothari Education Commission of 1964-65 recommended the uniform adoption all over the country of the 10+2+3 pattern with a Vocational stream at the plus two stage. It also emphasised the need for transferring the Pre-University Courses from the colleges to Secondary Schools by 1975-76. The switchover to this national pattern was ultimately adopted in Tamil Nadu in 1976, after great deliberations and on the recommendations of a high power committee in 1975. Thus; PUG was abolished with effect from the academic year 1979-80 in Tamil Nadu.

Government of Tamil Nadu devotes special attention for strengthening the higher education system in the State to respond to the emerging demands of the new century. It is a matter of great satisfaction that the graduates of the technical institutions in Tamil Nadu have shown outstanding performance in the industry, both in India and abroad. Many of them have become major entrepreneurs. The table-II indicates the educational institutions in Tamil Nadu from 1961 to 2011.

Table 2: Educational Institutions in Tamil Nadu - 2011

S.No	Types of Colleges	Government Constituent Colleges	Management		Total
			Aided	Self Financing (Unaided)	
1	Arts and Science Colleges	60	133	251	444
2	Physical Education	-	3	1	04
3	Oriental	-	10	-	10
4	Schools of Social work	-	2	-	02
5	Colleges of Education	7	14	22	43
	Total	67	162	274	503

Development of Universities and Colleges:

- At present, there are Twenty Three universities in Tamil Nadu. The universities are
- ✓ University of Madras
- ✓ Bharathiyar University
- ✓ Bharathidasan University
- ✓ Madurai Kamaraj University
- ✓ Manonmaniam Sundaranar University
- ✓ Periyar University
- ✓ Annamalai University
- ✓ Alagappa University
- ✓ Mother Teresa Women's University
- ✓ Tamil University
- ✓ Thiruvalluvar University
- ✓ Tamil Nadu Open University
- ✓ Tamil Nadu Physical Education and Sports University
- ✓ Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University
- ✓ Anna University - Chennai
- ✓ Anna University of Technology - Chennai
- ✓ Anna University of Technology, Coimbatore
- ✓ Anna University of Technology Tiruchirappalli
- ✓ Anna University of Technology, Tirunelveli
- ✓ Tamil Nadu Agricultural University

- ✓ Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University
- ✓ Tamil Nadu Dr. Ambedkar Law University
- ✓ Tamil Nadu Dr. MGR Medical University

Madras University:

The Madras University was founded in 1857 and the present Act in force is the Madras University Act of 1923. The other University Bills are shaped more or less on the basis of the provisions contained in the Madras University Act 1923. The affiliating university is an apex body, an examining and certifying university is an apex body, an examining and Certifying institution over the Students prepared by several Colleges scattered in its jurisdiction. On the contrary the unitary university is a single institution preparing, examining, and certifying the students who normally reside within the Campus for all the academic year(s).

Annamalai University:

Annamalai Chettiar's intention to develop Sri Meenakshi College, Chidambaram, into a unitary teaching institution was approved. In 1928, Sri Annamalai Chettiar offered to the State Government 20 lakhs of rupees for creating a new University besides 300 acres of land. The Annamalai University came into existence by an Act of the Legislature in 1929. As per Section 10(1) of the Annamalai University Act, the founder or his heir should be the Pro-Chancellor of the University. The Chancellor shall appoint the Vice-Chancellor from and panel of three names recommended by the founder or his heirs as per Section 12(1)59.

Madurai Kamarajar University:

The desire of the citizens of Madurai to have a University was fulfilled, when the Madurai University Centre was transformed into the Madurai University by an Act of the Madras State in 1965. The University was inaugurated on 6th February, 1966 with the jurisdiction over the districts of Madurai Ramanathapuram, Tirunelveli and Kanniyakumari.

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University:

The Agricultural School was opened at Saidapet, near Madras in 1876. Diploma certificate and Licenciate certificate courses were offered there. Later, this institution got merged with the Coimbatore Agricultural College in 1907. The need for orienting agricultural education in India, to solve the problems of the farmers. Perarignar Anna University of Technology With a view to fostering the growth and development of higher education and research in Engineering, Technology and allied Sciences, the Government of Tamil Nadu had established a unitary University, known as Perarignar Anna University of Technology on 4th September, 1978.61

Bharathiyar and Bharathidasan Universities:

Gajendragadkar Committee on University education expressed the view that not more than 30 or 40 colleges should be affiliated with a University. To reduce the burden of the University of Madras which had 110 affiliated colleges, the University Extension Centres at Coimbatore and Tiruchirappalli were upgraded as Universities of affiliating type 62. The University at Coimbatore was named after Bharathiyar and that of Tiruchirappalli after Bharathidasan.

Tamil University:

The popular demand about the scope for research in Tamil language and culture had made the Government of Tamil Nadu to consider the establishment of a Tamil University. A unanimous decision of starting the Tamil University was taken at the Fifth International Conference Seminar of Tamil Studies at Madurai in January, 1981. Thus a unitary Tamil University was inaugurated on 15th September, 1981 at Thanjavur 63.

Annai Therasa University:

In order to give expression to the views of Bharathiar that women should be provided with higher education, a women's University was proposed to be established by the Government of Tamil Nadu. An expert committee headed by Malcolm Adiseshiah, stressed the need of a women's University to provide higher education to women, to enable them to conduct research and to render advice about women's welfare. The women's University was inaugurated on 2nd March, 1984, at Kodaikanal and it was named after Mother Therasa, who has rendered invaluable service to the downtrodden64.

Administration of Universities in Tamil Nadu:

In general, the Vice-Chancellor is the head of the university and is responsible for formulating policies and reviewing the progress of the university. He has to deal with the twin sides of the university namely, the academic and administrative. In this task, he is ably assisted by the Syndicate, the Senate and the Academic Council in policy formulation. The Senate is empowered to determine the broad principles of university policy. The Syndicate as the highest body in the university set up carries out the directives of the Vice-Chancellor. The Academic Council is to advise the Senate and Syndicate on all academic matters65.

The Principal administrative officer of the University is the Registrar, who is the head of the University staff. He conducts the university correspondence and is the custodian of the records, the library, the common seal and such other property of the university as the Syndicate would commit to his charge. All the meetings of the Senate, Syndicate and Faculties are to be convened through the Registrar, who is to keep the record of the

proceedings of such meetings. He is appointed by the Syndicate subject to confirmation by the Senate. The structures of the administration of the universities are hierarchically patterned⁶⁶.

The Directorate of Collegiate Education:

A Committee of Public Instruction was appointed in 1823 and it had contemplated the establishment of schools and other institutions for the development of education in the Madras Presidency. The initial attempts of the British to provide higher education did not materialise and the Despatch of 1854, had established a Directorate of Public Instruction for the superintendence and direction of education.

In 1967, the nomenclature of the Director of Higher Education was changed as the Director of Collegiate Education. The Directorate of Collegiate Education was reorganized again in 1979. Six regional offices under the control of Deputy Directors were created and these are situated at Madras, Tiruchi, Coimbatore, Dharmapuri, Madurai and Tirunelveli⁶⁷. At present the higher Education is under the separate minister with designation as higher education minister. In the higher education ministry there is a Principal Secretary for higher education.

Affiliated Colleges:

According to the incorporating Act of 1857, the affiliation of colleges was an essential part of the system of liberal culture which was then proposed to be introduced. Brahmin's enlightened self-interest and non-Brahmin's opposition to the monopolistic attitudes of the Brahmins had permeated the educational arena of Tamil Nadu also, leading to proliferation of the institutional structures at the school and collegiate levels⁶⁸.

The relations between the University and its affiliated colleges were not very clearly defined. The unfortunate consequence was that ties between the university and its colleges were of the loosest type, and such responsibility as devolved on the university was shared by the department of education also. The favourable interaction between the government and the social groups in Tamil Nadu led to competitive educational enterprise.

In the post-Independence period there was a methodical growth in the structures and functions of the Madras University. When the Madras University became unwieldy, the growth centres became full-fledged universities by themselves. In spite of the fact that there were the creation of more and more universities, the advancement of knowledge in several areas of sciences, technology, medicine and social sciences demand more and more colleges for aggregation and dissemination of knowledge. That way, the universities in Tamil Nadu have properly responded to the requirements of the people. Logically, the qualified people look forward to the satisfaction of basic demands. Failure to provide them leads to dissatisfaction and dissonance.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

In Public and private educational institutions play various roles for delivering the educational service through both general and technical educations. Also mechanism/system needs to be enforced for governance and accountability to pupil's future education. However the proliferation of the structures demands properly qualified and trained personnel to operate the structures and the system. There are new challenges for educational systems in knowledge societies. This requires a responsive, future-focused education system, based on high expectations for successful outcomes amongst diverse learner groups. Also the public institutions and the private institutions to be framed a multi - functional systems in educational society. A clear understanding of the socio-political forces is essential for an enquiry in the educational process between education and social changes.

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